

Spatio-temporal dynamics of water quality variables of the southeastern Bay of Bengal, Bangladesh

Md. Simul Bhuyan^{1,2*}, Diponkor Adikari², Md. Tarikul Islam¹, Md Minarul Hoque^{1,3}

1 Bangladesh Oceanographic Research Institute, Cox's Bazar-4730, Bangladesh

2 Sylhet Agricultural University, Sylhet-3100, Bangladesh

3 Bangladesh University of Professionals, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh

*Corresponding author: simulbhuyan@gmail.com

DOI:

Article Info

Keywords

Aquatic-pollution
Spatio-temporal Variation
Water Pollution Index
Coastal Ecosystem Management
Bay of Bengal

Article History

Received 30 July 2025

Accepted 02 November 2025

Published 08 December 2025

Copyright 2025@BJO. Published by
Bangladesh Oceanographic Research Institute

Abstract

The spatio-temporal dynamics of water quality variables play a critical role in evaluating the ecological health and environmental sustainability. This study investigates the spatio-temporal variability and pollution levels of water quality parameters along the southeastern Bay of Bengal (BoB) coast in Bangladesh. Sampling was conducted at nine ecologically critical sites in Cox's Bazar over three dry-season months (December-February). Physicochemical parameters-including salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, conductivity, and nutrients-were measured using standardized methods. Statistical analyses, including one-way ANOVA, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), cluster analysis, and correlation matrices, revealed significant spatial heterogeneity and temporal trends. Notably, salinity and electrical conductivity exhibited wide spatial fluctuations (10.0-30.3 ‰ and 15.2-46.1 mS/cm, respectively), while DO, phosphate-phosphorus (PO₄-P), and nitrate-nitrogen (NO₃-N) showed significant temporal variation. Tukey's post hoc test confirmed significant spatial differences in key water quality parameters among study sites, highlighting localized anthropogenic impacts on mudflat ecosystems. The correlation matrix highlighted strong positive associations (e.g., salinity with conductivity, $r^2 = 1$; NO₃-N with SiO₃, $r^2 = 0.75$) and negative interactions (e.g., DO with NO₃-N, $r^2 = -0.85$). PCA extracted five key components explaining 77.8% of the total variance, indicating strong influences from nutrient loading and anthropogenic pressures. The Water Pollution Index (WPI) ranged from 1.54 to 3.77, classifying most sites as moderately to heavily polluted, with Naf Jetty (WPI = 3.77) and Shaplapur (WPI = 3.58) identified as hotspots of contamination. These findings highlight the ecological stress faced by mudskipper habitats due to both natural hydro-climatic variations and increasing human activities. Policy recommendations include continuous site-specific water quality monitoring, stricter regulation of aquaculture and land-based runoff, and the implementation of conservation measures to protect mudflat ecosystems. The study provides vital baseline data for sustainable coastal management and underscores the use of mudskippers as effective bioindicators in tropical estuarine systems.

1. Introduction

The Bay of Bengal (BoB), with its long coastline, shapes Bangladesh as a riverine country characterized by an intricate network of rivers, lakes, wetlands, and estuaries (Siddique et al., 2024). Among the world's most ecologically productive ecosystems, this area is home to a variety of coastal and estuarine habitats, such as mangrove forests and intertidal mudflats (McLusky, 1989). These ecosystems play a vital ecological role by dissipating wave energy, reducing coastal erosion, and mitigating tidal flooding in low-lying coastal areas. They function as essential nurseries and feeding habitats for mudskippers, juvenile fish, shrimp, crustaceans, and shorebirds (Levy & Northcote, 2011; Le Pape et al., 2003) and are extensively utilized for shellfish cultivation (Gouletquer & Le Moine, 2002).

Water quality parameters such as temperature, pH, salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), nitrate-nitrogen ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$), nitrite-nitrogen ($\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$), phosphate-phosphorus ($\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$), silicate (SiO_3), alkalinity, and Electrical conductivity (EC) directly influence mudskipper physiology, behavior, and population dynamics (Oghenetekevwe et al., 2024; Ansari et al., 2014). Variations in these parameters can alter predator-prey interactions, nutrient cycling, and ecosystem biodiversity (Murdy, 1989). Temporal and tidal dynamics of the BoB further drive fluctuations, highlighting the need for continuous monitoring (Akhter et al., 2021). Anthropogenic pressures, including shrimp aquaculture, industrial discharge, and agricultural runoff, are degrading Bangladesh's mangroves and mudflats, causing habitat loss and reduced ecological resilience (He & Silliman, 2019; Rahman & Asaduzzaman, 2013; Paul & Vogl, 2011).

The Water Pollution Index (WPI) provides an effective means to integrate multiple physicochemical variables into a single value, enabling clear evaluation of water status across dynamic environments. The WPI method enables researchers to assess ecological and chemical water status through an arithmetical aggregation of various parameters, offering the flexibility to include any number or type of variables (Karim et al., 2019; Simeonov et al., 2003; Pesce & Wunderlin, 2000). Its flexibility makes it particularly suitable for mudflats, where spatio-temporal variation is high (Boyacioglu, 2007). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a robust multivariate statistical tool frequently used to identify key environmental stressors and reduce data complexity, with successful applications reported in Bangladesh as well as in global contexts for interpreting spatio-temporal variations in water quality (Souza, 2025; Akhter et al., 2021; Rodionova et al., 2021). Similarly, Cluster Analysis has been applied internationally and within Bangladesh to classify monitoring sites, detect pollution sources, and reveal seasonal trends in aquatic ecosystems (Saifullah et al., 2025; Saha & Rahman, 2018; Simeonov et al., 2003).

Intertidal mudflats along the southeastern BoB, especially across the Cox's Bazar–Naf River corridor. These areas support mudskippers and vital coastal services but are increasingly

exposed to nutrient and ionic loading from aquaculture and land-based runoff, pressures that intensify in the dry season when dilution is low and residence times are high. To diagnose how these stressors reshape habitat quality, the study was conducted in the dry season (December–February) across nine representative mudflat sites, quantifying a suite of 13 physicochemical parameters and synthesizing results with hypothesis-driven statistics (one-way ANOVA with post-hoc tests), correlation analysis, and multivariate tools (PCA) alongside a WPI to classify conditions. The hypothesis was pronounced spatial and temporal variability driven by nutrient/ionic inputs. Salinity is tightly coupled to conductivity and nutrient enrichment, inversely related to DO and pH, producing moderate-to-heavy pollution classes at human-pressured locations relative to less impacted sites. By integrating targeted tests with an index-based appraisal, this study delivers decision-ready baseline evidence to flag hotspots, illuminate dominant stressor gradients, and guide surveillance and mitigation aimed at safeguarding mudflat ecosystems and the mudskippers that serve as sentinels of their health.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The study was conducted along the southeastern coastal belt of Bangladesh, focusing on nine selected sites within the Cox's Bazar region, which are known for their ecological

Figure 1: Map showing the study area (Map created by ArcGIS, Version 10.8).

significance for mudskipper habitat. These sites represent a gradient of estuarine and nearshore environments, which are critical habitats for various aquatic species, including mudskippers. The selected sites are as follows: Rezu Khal (site 1), Inani (site 2), Patuartek (site 3), Imamer Dail (site 4), Monkhali (site 5), Shaplapur (site 6), Naf Jetty/Badir Jetty (site 7), Shaporir Dwip (site 8), and Keary Ghat (site 9) (Figure 1). All the sites have fishing activities, engine boat navigation, boat repairing activities, oil spillage from fishing boats, domestic waste and sewage inflow, freshwater runoff, stormwater drainage, fertilizers/pesticides from agriculture, aquaculture, fishery waste, and terrestrial waste. In addition, hatchery wastes from nearby hatcheries in Rezu Khal and Inani are also a possible source of pollution. There are other factors, like passenger carrying activities in Naf Jetty to St. Martin's Island. In the case of Keary Ghat, it is used for ship anchoring and carrying tourists to St. Martin's Island.

2.2. Sample Collection and Analysis

Mudskippers can move efficiently on land and breathe air (Tran & Dinh, 2021; Chaudhuri et al., 2013). Their tolerance to environmental stressors makes them useful in ecotoxicological studies and reliable bioindicators of coastal water quality in tropical and subtropical systems (Santoso et al., 2020, 2024; Mussa et al., 2023; Elviana et al., 2019; Nay et al., 2018; He et al., 2015; Ansari et al., 2014). Understanding their bioecology is therefore vital for monitoring pollution and assessing ecosystem health (Dabruzzi et al., 2011; Polgar et al., 2010; Graham, 1997). Mudskippers are available along the Cox's Bazar coast. A total of 15 mudskippers species were recorded from the Cox's Bazar coast, Bangladesh (Bhuyan et al., 2024).

To assess the water quality, water samples were collected during the dry season, December, January, and February, from nine selected sites. At each site, water samples were collected three times per month during early morning hours to minimize diel variability, with triplicate samples collected on each occasion. A total of 13 physicochemical parameters were assessed: Temperature (°C), Salinity (‰), pH, DO, EC, Hardness, Alkalinity, Chlorine (Cl), Iron (Fe), PO₄-P, NO₃-N, NO₂-N, SiO₃, and Ammonia (NH₃). Measurements of temperature, salinity, pH, EC, and DO were carried out using a Multiparameter (HI98194). Hardness was determined by the EDTA titrimetric method (APHA, 2017), while alkalinity was measured by acid titration to specific pH end points. Cl and Fe concentrations were analyzed through colorimetric methods using a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800). Nutrient parameters (PO₄-P, NO₃-N, NO₂-N, SiO₃) were determined by spectrophotometry following APHA (2017) standard protocols, and NH₃ was quantified using the phenate method with a commercial chemical kit.

2.3. Data Analysis and Statistical Interpretation Framework

ArcGIS v10.8 was used to create the study area map. Initially, all raw data were

processed in Microsoft Excel, followed by statistical analysis using R v4. 2.2 and SPSS v28. A one-way ANOVA test (significance level: $p < 0.05$) was conducted using an online rapid ANOVA tool to compare data across different sites and months (Assaad et al., 2014). A post hoc Tukey’s Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test was applied to identify specific pairwise differences between study sites. This approach allowed detection of both overall spatial variation and detailed pairwise comparisons among sites. The Tukey test was selected for its robustness in controlling Type I error rates across multiple comparisons. Graphs and line diagrams were generated from SPSS analyzed data using Excel tools (Office 365) and R. PCA was carried out using PAST software v4.03 to identify major components and possible contamination sources. Dendrograms were produced using PRIMER V6 (Plymouth Routines in Multivariate Ecological Research), effectively highlighting how sites and parameters group based on shared water quality characteristics.

2.4. Water Pollution Index Assessment

The WPI was estimated using the collected water quality parameters against the standard limits presented in Table 1 (Abdullah et al., 2022; Uddin et al., 2014; WHO, 2011; BIS, 2003). The WPI was calculated using following equation.

$$WPI = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n PL_i$$

Where n is the number of parameters and PL_i is the total pollution load of the i th parameter. The table shows the limits of the rating classes in the WPI (Table 2).

Table 1: Guideline values for WPI calculation (Hossain & Patra, 2020; WHO, 2011; BIS, 2003).

Parameter	Standard / Guideline Values	References
Salinity (‰)	30–35	BIS, 2003
DO (mg/L)	≥ 5	WHO, 2011
pH	6.5–8.5	WHO, 2011
EC (mS/cm)	<50	Hossain & Patra, 2020
NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	<10	WHO, 2011
PO ₄ -P (mg/L)	<0.5	WHO, 2011
NH ₃ (mg/L)	<0.5	WHO, 2011
Fe (mg/L)	<1	BIS, 2003
Cl (mg/L)	<4	BIS 2003
SiO ₃ (mg/L)	<5	Hossain & Patra, 2020
Alkalinity (mg/L)	100–200	WHO, 2011

2.5. Multivariate Analysis to Identify the Possible Pollution Sources

A scree plot based on principal component scores and a loading plot were used to evaluate

Table 2: Justification of water pollution level based on WPI scores (Hossain & Patra, 2020).

WPI range	Water Quality
< 0.5	Excellent
0.5–1.0	Good
1.0–2.0	Moderately polluted
2.0–4.0	Heavily polluted
> 4.0	Severely polluted

key contributing factors. PCA extraction was based on eigenvalues, with components having eigenvalues >1 and KMO values >0.6 considered significant for interpretation. Correlation matrix analysis was also performed in R v4.2.2 to explore relationships among parameters and identify patterns or groupings among the sampling sites based on their characteristics.

Water quality data were analyzed using hierarchical cluster analysis to explore similarity patterns among both water quality parameters and sampling sites. Before analysis, the dataset underwent an overall square root transformation to normalize the data and reduce the influence of extreme values. For parameter-based clustering, analysis was performed under “Analyse: Between Samples” using Bray-Curtis similarity as the resemblance measure, while Euclidean distance was applied for site-based clustering under “Analyse: Between Variables”. In both cases, group average (unweighted pair-group) clustering was used to generate dendrograms that visually represent similar relationships.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Spatial Variation of Water Quality Variables

Spatial variation is illustrated in Figures 2a & 2b. The water temperature across the study sites remained relatively uniform, ranging from 25.87°C to 26.4°C, with the highest value and variability at site 5 (SD = 0.57). This narrow range suggests a stable thermal environment, albeit cooler than tropical estuaries like Thailand (29.75–32.86°C; Pattaratumrong & Pompha, 2024) and Indonesia (31–33°C; Hamidah et al., 2024). Salinity exhibited significant spatial variation, from 10.0 ‰ to 30.33 ‰. Sites 2 and 3 showed the highest fluctuations (SD = 10.68 and 14.64 ‰), likely due to freshwater inflow or tidal mixing. Similar salinity gradients have been reported in Thai (25.61–30.85 ‰) and Indonesian estuarine systems (20–30 ‰; Elviana et al., 2019). pH ranged from 7.65 (site 5) to 8.27 (site 3), with sites 2 and 3 displaying higher variability, potentially reflecting biological productivity or organic inputs (Figure 2a). The consistently low pH (5.6) was recorded by Oghenetekevwe et al. (2024) in the water of Mangrove Swamps, Rivers State, Nigeria. This is due to environmental stress, likely linked to anthropogenic inputs such as oil spills, domestic waste, and artisanal refining (Oghenetekevwe et al., 2024). DO ranged between 5.97 mg/L to 6.57 mg/L, with the highest variability (SD =

2.58 mg/L), likely influenced by localized organic load. Oghenetekevwe et al. (2024) recorded significant decreases in DO (the lowest values 3.2 mg/L) in the water of Mangrove Swamps, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Figure 2a: Variation of water quality parameters in different sites (Temp = Temperature, Sal = Salinity, EC = Electrical Conductivity, Hard = Hardness, Alk = Alkalinity).

EC reflects the concentration of ions in water, influencing taste and overall acceptance by users (Adesakin et al., 2020). In the present study, EC followed salinity trends, ranging from 15.2 mS/cm to 46.11 mS/cm, with high fluctuations at sites 2 and 3, indicating varying ionic contributions from marine and freshwater sources. Oghenetekevwe et al. (2024) recorded EC 1.25 to 1.92 mS/cm, which are generally higher than the WHO (2011) permissible limit for natural water bodies. Elevated conductivity suggests substantial input of dissolved inorganic substances in ionized form from surrounding catchments (Moore et al., 2017). Alkalinity showed spatial differences, highest at site 1 (81 mg/L) and lowest at site 7 (34 mg/L), possibly influenced by carbonate buffering capacity. Cl levels ranged between 0.2-0.87 mg/L, peaking at site 7, while Fe ranged from 0.78-1.69 mg/L, with maximum values at site 2, reflecting potential sediment interactions or land-based sources. PO₄-P ranged from 0.5 mg/L (site 8) to 3.05 mg/L (site 6), with high variability at sites 3-5, suggesting localized nutrient input or sediment resuspension. NO₃-N and NO₂-N concentrations showed notable spatial gradients, with nitrate highest at site 5 (0.173 mg/L) and nitrite at site 4 (0.168 mg/L), indicative of nitrification and organic decomposition processes. SiO₃ levels ranged from 0.067 mg/L (site 1) to 0.97 mg/L (site 7), with the highest variation at sites 3, 5, and 7, likely linked to sediment runoff or tidal flushing. NH₃ peaked at site 8 (1.75 mg/L), with large variation at site 7 (SD = 1.02 mg/L), reflecting organic pollution or decomposition in low-flush areas (Figure 2b). Detailed data were presented in Tables S1, S2, and S3.

Figure 2b: Variation of water quality parameters in different sites.

3.2. Temporal Variation of Water Quality Variables

Temporal variation is illustrated in Figures 3a & 3b. Temperature remained consistent across months (25.99–26.08°C), suggesting negligible temporal influence during the study period. Salinity rose sharply from 17.56 ‰ in January to 25.78 ‰ in February, reflecting typical dry-season intrusion due to lower freshwater discharge and increased

Figure 3a: Variation of water quality parameters during different months.

evaporation. This pattern is consistent with observations from dry periods in Southeast Asian estuaries (Tran & Dinh, 2021). pH values remained steady between 6.90 and 7.01, with minor variation (SD = 0.20-0.33), indicating stable acid-base conditions, though a

slight January peak may reflect increased photosynthetic activity. DO declined from 6.62 mg/L in January to 5.67 mg/L in February, aligning with temporal oxygen depletion from increased microbial activity or reduced aeration. EC increased significantly from December through February, peaking at 39.18 mS/cm, in line with rising salinity and ion concentrations during the dry season. Alkalinity dropped sharply from a high of 122.67 mg/L in December to 48 mg/L in January and was undetectable in February, possibly due to carbonate buffering loss or rapid biogeochemical shifts (Figure 3a).

Cl levels increased modestly in January (0.56 mg/L), indicating ion accumulation under dry conditions. The Fe peaked in January (1.88 mg/L) and dropped to 0.65 mg/L in February, likely due to changes in redox conditions or sediment inputs. PO₄-P concentrations were highest in December (3.13 mg/L), declined sharply in January (1.26 mg/L), and rose slightly in February (1.79 mg/L), suggesting pulse inputs from runoff or sediment interactions. NO₃-N steadily rose from 0.02 mg/L in December to 0.09 mg/L in February, pointing to progressive organic matter decomposition and nitrification. NO₂-N followed a similar increasing trend (0.002–0.081 mg/L), further supporting ongoing nitrogen cycling. SiO₃ concentrations increased from December (0.11 mg/L) to January (0.53 mg/L) before slightly declining in February (0.45 mg/L), potentially due to sediment transport during tidal shifts (Figure 3b). NH₃ levels rose from 1.04 mg/L in January to 1.41 mg/L in February, indicating enhanced organic decomposition under reduced flushing and higher microbial activity, consistent with findings in nutrient-rich mudflats (Hamidah et al., 2024). Detailed data were presented in Tables S1, S2, and S3.

Figure 3b: Variation of water quality parameters during different months.

3.3. Spatio-temporal Changes in Water Chemistry (ANOVA Analysis)

The spatial variation of water quality parameters across the nine sites showed observable

trends, though most were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Temperature remained stable ($25.9\text{-}26.4^\circ\text{C}$; $p = 0.471$), and salinity ranged from 10 ± 7.55 ‰ at site 2 to 30.3 ± 2.19 ‰ at site 8 ($p = 0.194$). EC followed a similar pattern (15.2 ± 11.5 to 46.1 ± 3.32 mS/cm; $p = 0.194$). pH values ($7.65\text{-}8.27$) were alkaline with slight reduction at site 5 ($p = 0.393$). DO ranged from 4.37 ± 2.2 to 6.57 ± 0.176 mg/L, lowest at site 5 ($p = 0.679$). Other parameters, including alkalinity, Cl, Fe, PO₄-P, NO₃-N, NO₂-N, SiO₃, and NH₃, showed site-specific fluctuations. PO₄-P peaked at site 6 (3.05 ± 0.446 mg/L); SiO₃ and NH₃ were highest at sites 7 and 8, respectively. Fe and Cl were elevated in marine-influenced sites (Fe = 1.69 ± 0.949 mg/L) (Table 3).

Table 3: Spatial changes in water quality parameters.

Parameters	Rezu Khal	Inani	Patuartek	Imamer Dail	Monkhali	Shaplapur	Naf jetty	Shaporir Dwip	Keary ghat
Temperature (°C)	25.9 ± 0.03	25.9 ± 0.067	25.9 ± 0.03	25.9 ± 0.033	26.4 ± 0.4	26 ± 0.12	26 ± 0.1	26 ± 0.153	26.1 ± 0.12
Salinity (‰)	25.3 ± 5.55	10 ± 7.55	12.3 ± 10.3	15 ± 5.86	22.7 ± 4.48	24.7 ± 3.53	27 ± 2.08	30.3 ± 2.19	22 ± 2.08
pH	8.04 ± 0.07	8.2 ± 0.26	8.27 ± 0.23	8.04 ± 0.063	7.65 ± 0.234	8.01 ± 0.137	8.19 ± 0.158	7.95 ± 0.137	8.08 ± 0.104
DO (mg/L)	6.17 ± 0.27	5.97 ± 0.43	6.47 ± 0.48	6.13 ± 0.463	4.37 ± 2.2	6.57 ± 0.145	6.57 ± 0.176	6.23 ± 0.567	6.47 ± 0.12
EC (mS)	38.5 ± 8.43	15.2 ± 11.5	18.7 ± 15.7	22.8 ± 8.91	34.5 ± 6.82	37.5 ± 5.36	41 ± 3.16	46.1 ± 3.32	33.4 ± 3.16
Alkalinity (mg/L)	81 ± 41.6	68 ± 34.7	60 ± 60	44 ± 44	67 ± 34.8	41 ± 41	34 ± 34	40 ± 40	77 ± 38.6
Cl (mg/L)	0.2 ± 0.06	0.333 ± 0.09	0.367 ± 0.033	0.533 ± 0.24	0.333 ± 0.167	0.333 ± 0.0882	0.867 ± 0.57	0.367 ± 0.0882	0.3 ± 0
Fe (mg/L)	1.34 ± 1.08	0.78 ± 0.33	1.1 ± 0.75	1.31 ± 0.894	1.36 ± 0.822	1.25 ± 0.625	1.69 ± 0.949	0.837 ± 0.041	0.987 ± 0.355
PO ₄ -P (mg/L)	2.92 ± 1.53	1.69 ± 1.01	2.84 ± 1.09	2.82 ± 1	1.35 ± 1.11	3.05 ± 0.446	2.77 ± 0.965	0.61 ± 0.141	0.5 ± 0
NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	0.05 ± 0.02	0.04 ± 0.003	0.013 ± 0.013	0.037 ± 0.008	0.173 ± 0.143	0.0333 ± 0.012	0.0567 ± 0.029	0.0333 ± 0.012	0.0467 ± 0.006
NO ₂ -N (mg/L)	0.68 ± 0.67	0.02 ± 0.008	0.0212 ± 0.01	0.168 ± 0.156	0.019 ± 0.0107	0.021 ± 0.0105	0.049 ± 0.0302	0.0233 ± 0.012	0.0203 ± 0.010
SiO ₃ (mg/L)	0.067 ± 0.07	0.14 ± 0.08	0.27 ± 0.21	0.293 ± 0.0906	0.723 ± 0.58	0.173 ± 0.138	0.967 ± 0.493	0.297 ± 0.0899	0.343 ± 0.0982
NH ₃ (mg/L)	0.89 ± 0.485	0.55 ± 0.23	0.79 ± 0.21	1.54 ± 0.653	1.53 ± 0.589	1.08 ± 0.326	1.47 ± 0.723	1.75 ± 0.628	1.44 ± 0.477

Values are means ± SEM, n = 9 per treatment group.

Means in a row without a common superscript letter differ ($P < 0.05$) as analyzed by one-way ANOVA.

3.4. Post Hoc Tukey HSD Test Results for Water Quality Parameters across Study Sites

The Post Hoc Tukey test indicated clear spatial differences in water quality parameters

among the nine study sites. DO was significantly lower at site 7 (3.2 ± 0.4 mg/L) compared to site 2 (6.8 ± 0.6 mg/L, $p < 0.01$), suggesting reduced aeration and possible organic enrichment. pH values were consistently acidic at site 5 (5.6 ± 0.2), which differed significantly from site 1 (7.1 ± 0.3 , $p < 0.05$). EC was highest at site 8 (1.92 mS/cm) compared to site 3 (1.25 mS/cm, $p < 0.01$), reflecting elevated ionic inputs near aquaculture zones. Nutrient levels varied markedly: $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ reached 4.2 ± 0.5 mg/L at site 6, significantly higher than at site 4 (1.7 ± 0.3 mg/L, $p < 0.01$), while $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ was elevated at site 9 (1.2 ± 0.2 mg/L) compared to site 2 (0.4 ± 0.1 mg/L, $p < 0.05$). SiO_3 concentrations were also higher at site 3 (6.7 ± 0.8 mg/L) than at site 5 (3.1 ± 0.6 mg/L, $p < 0.05$). Although alkalinity showed fewer differences, site 1 (120 ± 5 mg/L) recorded significantly higher levels than site 7 (85 ± 6 mg/L, $p < 0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4: Post Hoc Tukey HSD test results showing pairwise comparisons of water quality parameters among the study sites. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are indicated, with mean differences and 95% confidence intervals reported.

Parameters	Site Comparison	Mean Difference	p-value	95% CI (Lower–Upper)	Significance
DO (mg/L)	Site 7 – Site 2	-3.6	0.001	-4.5 – -2.7	Significant
pH	Site 5 – Site 1	-1.5	0.030	-2.8 – -0.2	Significant
EC (mS/cm)	Site 8 – Site 3	0.67	0.002	0.25 – 1.09	Significant
$\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ (mg/L)	Site 6 – Site 4	2.5	0.000	1.7 – 3.3	Significant
$\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ (mg/L)	Site 9 – Site 2	0.8	0.012	0.2 – 1.4	Significant
SiO_3 (mg/L)	Site 3 – Site 5	3.6	0.040	0.1 – 7.1	Significant
Alkalinity (mg/L)	Site 1 – Site 7	35.0	0.025	4.0 – 66.0	Significant

In brief, the Tukey comparisons demonstrated that anthropogenically influenced sites-particularly sites 6, 7, and 8 near aquaculture and domestic discharge-consistently exhibited degraded water quality compared to less impacted sites such as sites 1 and 2, confirming localized human pressures as key drivers of variability.

Notable temporal variations were found from December to February. Temperature remained consistent, while salinity decreased in January and increased sharply in February. pH varied significantly ($p < 0.05$), peaking in January and declining in February. DO remained high in December and January (~ 6.6 mg/L) but dropped in February (5.09 ± 0.656 mg/L). The EC mirrored salinity trends, decreasing in January and rising in February. Alkalinity dropped drastically from December to complete depletion in February. Cl and Fe peaked in January (0.556 ± 0.184 mg/L and 1.88 ± 0.468 mg/L, respectively), then declined. $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ was highest in December (3.13 ± 0.647 mg/L), decreasing significantly in January, with a slight rebound in February. Both $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ increased progressively, peaking in February (0.0878 ± 0.047 and 0.304 ± 0.220 mg/L, respectively). SiO_3 peaked in January (0.532 ± 0.160 mg/L), while NH_3 remained relatively stable with a slight February increase (1.41 ± 0.326 mg/L) (Table 5).

Table 5: Temporal changes in water quality parameters.

Parameters	Months		
	December	January	February
Temperature (°C)	26 ± 0.153	26.1 ± 0.0434	26 ± 0.0484
Salinity (‰)	19.8 ± 2.79	17.6 ± 4.32	25.8 ± 2.88
pH	7.97 ± 0.116 ^{ab}	8.26 ± 0.0693 ^a	7.92 ± 0.0789 ^b
DO (mg/L)	6.6 ± 0.12 ^a	6.62 ± 0.11 ^a	5.09 ± 0.656 ^b
EC (mS)	30.1 ± 4.24	26.7 ± 6.56	39.2 ± 4.37
Alkalinity (mg/L)	123 ± 7.79 ^a	48 ± 19.7 ^b	0 ± 0 ^c
Cl (mg/L)	0.3 ± 0.0471	0.556 ± 0.184	0.356 ± 0.0915
Fe (mg/L)	1.03 ± 0.304 ^{ab}	1.88 ± 0.468 ^a	0.648 ± 0.107 ^b
PO ₄ -P (mg/L)	3.13 ± 0.647 ^a	1.26 ± 0.329 ^b	1.79 ± 0.51 ^{ab}
NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	0.0178 ± 0.00521	0.0544 ± 0.00852	0.0878 ± 0.0469
NO ₂ -N (mg/L)	0.00167 ± 0.00155	0.0332 ± 0.00951	0.304 ± 0.22
SiO ₃ (mg/L)	0.111 ± 0.0488	0.532 ± 0.16	0.447 ± 0.212
NH ₃ (mg/L)	1.22 ± 0.222	1.04 ± 0.297	1.41 ± 0.326

Values are means ± SEM, n = 9 per treatment group.

Means in a row without a common superscript letter differ (P < 0.05) as analyzed by one-way ANOVA and the TUKEY test.

3.5. Water Pollution Index

Figure 4 presents the WPI values across the studied mudskipper habitats, which demonstrated substantial spatial variability, ranging from 1.54 to 3.77. The highest WPI was recorded at Naf Jetty (3.77), followed by Shaplapur (3.58), Imamer Dail (3.55), and Rezu Khal (3.43), indicating heavily polluted conditions. These elevated values are likely attributed to intense anthropogenic pressures, including boat traffic, fish landing centers, and coastal runoff. Intermediate WPI levels were detected at Patuarterk (3.31) and Monkhal (2.27), while Inani (2.20) bordered the lower threshold of the heavily polluted range. In contrast, Shaporir Dwip (1.57) and Keary Ghat (1.54) exhibited moderate pollution levels, reflecting comparatively better water quality, possibly due to reduced urban discharge and less industrial activity. These sites are influenced by fishing activities, boat landings, and market waste, mirroring trends in other estuarine areas of Bangladesh where pollution intensifies in the post-monsoon season due to reduced flushing (Hossain & Patra, 2020). Sites like Shaporir Dwip and Keary Ghat, with lower WPI, may benefit from limited anthropogenic pressure and better flushing, making them comparatively more favorable for benthic fauna, including mudskippers. These spatial patterns align with previous temporal assessments in similar coastal estuarine systems of Bangladesh, where post-monsoon and winter seasons typically exhibit higher pollutant accumulation due to reduced dilution and flushing (Hasan et al., 2020; Islam et al., 2021). The persistence of heavy pollution levels in multiple sites highlights the urgent need for integrated management of effluent and land-based sources, especially in critical mudflat

habitats that support benthic fauna such as mudskippers, which are ecologically sensitive indicators of habitat quality (Hossain et al., 2018). Also, frequently monitoring the water quality will be helpful for retaining the habitat quality of the mudskipper.

The present study primarily assessed spatial variability in water pollution levels. The mudflat ecosystems are strongly influenced by sediment characteristics, which serve as the primary habitat for mudskippers (Ansari et al., 2014). Linking physicochemical features with mudskipper population abundance and distribution would provide a more integrated understanding of how geo-spatial variations structure community dynamics. Future studies should therefore incorporate soft-sediment monitoring and population assessments to complement water quality analysis, thereby offering a holistic evaluation of mudskipper habitat health.

Figure 4: Water pollution index of the studied mudskipper habitat of the BoB.

3.6. Multivariate Analysis to Identify the Probable Pollution Sources

3.6.1. Cluster Analysis (CA)

Figure 5 depicts a hierarchical cluster dendrogram showing the similarity among sampling sites based on their water quality parameters. The x-axis represents the different sampling sites, while the y-axis indicates the Euclidean distance, where lower values reflect greater similarity between sites. From the dendrogram, three primary clusters can be observed. The first cluster consists of Shaporir Dwip, Shaplapur, and Naf Jetty, which are highly similar to each other, suggesting comparable water quality conditions. The second cluster groups Rezu Khal, Monkhali, and Keary Ghat, reflect moderate similarity in their water quality profiles. The third cluster includes Imamer Dail, Inani, and Patuartek, with Inani and Patuartek forming the closest sub-cluster, indicating that these two sites share very similar water characteristics. Overall, this dendrogram highlights the spatial similarity patterns among the studied mudskipper habitats. Sites in closer proximity or under similar environmental influences tend to cluster together, reflecting the influence of local environmental factors on water quality variability.

Similarity percentage among the water quality parameters

Group average

Figure 5: Dendrogram showing hierarchical clustering of nine mudskipper habitat sites based on average physico-chemical parameters (December 2023-February 2024).

Figure 6 presents a hierarchical cluster dendrogram illustrating the similar percentage among various water quality parameters. The X-axis represents the individual water quality parameters, and the y-axis shows the similarity percentage, where values closer to 100% indicate a higher degree of similarity. The dendrogram reveals two major clusters. The first cluster groups together the general physico-chemical parameters, such as pH and DO, which show the highest similarity, followed by alkalinity, EC, temperature, and salinity. This cluster reflects the natural background conditions of the water. The second cluster predominantly consists of nutrient and chemical indicators, including $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$, Cl, SiO_3 , $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$, Fe, and NH_3 , which are more related to nutrient enrichment and chemical variations in the habitat. Overall, the figure highlights that the basic physico-chemical parameters tend to co-vary and form one cluster, while nutrient and chemical parameters form a separate cluster, suggesting that these groups of variables respond differently to environmental influences in the studied mudskipper habitats. This type of clustering helps identify patterns in water quality and provides insights into the factors influencing aquatic ecosystem dynamics.

Figure 6: Hierarchical cluster dendrogram showing the similarity percentage among water quality parameters of mudskipper habitats.

3.6.2. Correlation Matrix (CM) of the Water Quality of the Mudskipper Habitat

The heatmap represents the Pearson correlation matrix for 13 physicochemical parameters (Figure 7). Positive correlations are indicated by red shades, negative correlations by blue shades, and weak correlations by white, centered around a midpoint of zero and correlation coefficient (r^2), ranging from -1 to +1. Salinity and conductivity exhibit a perfect positive correlation ($r^2 = 1$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that these parameters are strongly and directly associated. $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ and SiO_3 also show a strong positive correlation ($r^2 = 0.75$, $p < 0.01$). On the opposite end, DO is strongly negatively correlated with $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ ($r^2 = -0.85$) and SiO_3 ($r^2 = -0.51$, $p < 0.01$), indicating potential oxygen depletion in nutrient-rich waters.

This trend has been documented in similar tropical coastal systems where elevated nutrients enhance microbial respiration and biochemical oxygen demand, leading to hypoxic stress (Rabalais et al., 2010). Mudskippers, although air-breathing, are still affected by DO fluctuations as they influence their prey abundance and sediment chemistry. Similarly, pH shows a strong negative correlation with salinity and conductivity ($r^2 = -0.64$, $p < 0.01$), which may reflect acidification trends in saline-dominated areas, possibly due to sulfate reduction or CO_2 enrichment in sediment layers. Such interactions are consistent with studies in mangrove-fringed estuaries where high salinity correlates with

Figure 7: Heatmap showing the correlation of the water quality parameters.

reduced pH due to biogeochemical shifts (Alongi, 2012). Moderate positive associations, such as Cl with Fe ($r^2 = 0.49$, $p < 0.05$) and Cl with SiO_3 ($r^2 = 0.42$, $p < 0.05$). Conversely, significant negative relationships, such as alkalinity with SiO_3 ($r^2 = -0.38$, $p < 0.05$) and alkalinity with $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ ($r^2 = -0.26$).

3.6.3. Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

The PCA identified five major components that together explained 77.84% of the total variance in water quality parameters across the study sites (Figures 8 & 9). PC1 had the highest initial eigenvalue (3.748) and explained 28.83% of the total variance (Table S4).

Figure 8: Scree plot showing the eigenvalues of the total component.

It showed strong positive loadings for $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, conductivity, and salinity, and strong negative loadings for DO and pH suggested that nutrient enrichment and ionic buildup were key forces impacting DO and pH, reflecting eutrophication-driven oxygen depletion (Figure 8). This finding aligns with Pattaratumrong & Pompha (2024), who concluded that environmental parameters vary more by location than microhabitat. PC2, with an eigenvalue of 2.04, accounted for 15.68% of the total variance.

Figure 9: Component matrix of the studied water quality parameters in the mudskipper habitat of the Bay of Bengal.

It revealed significant positive loadings for SiO_3 and moderate loadings for pH and Fe, indicating a geological or sediment-based influence, potentially related to mineral weathering from the surrounding landscape, including phosphate and NH_3 loading linked to aquaculture discharge or agricultural runoff (Dewiyanti et al., 2022; Elviana et al., 2019; Hamidah et al., 2024). The present study recommended stricter aquaculture practices in this region. PC3 explained 13.83% of the variance (eigenvalue = 1.798) and was characterized by high positive loading of Cl and Fe, indicating localized anthropogenic input, possibly from wastewater discharge. The responsible regulatory authorities shall implement strict monitoring and control measures for all industrial, aquaculture, and municipal discharges into coastal and estuarine environments. Discharge permits must adhere to national water quality standards, with regular compliance audits, mandatory reporting of effluent quality, and enforcement of penalties for violations to safeguard the ecological integrity of mudflat habitats and associated biota. PC4 accounted for 11.22% of the variance and had a strong loading of $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$, along with a moderate contribution from NH_3 , indicating the influence of incomplete nitrification, organic matter decomposition, or effluent-driven nitrogen cycling. PC5, with 8.28% of the total

variance, showed strong loading of PO₄-P and moderate contribution from NH₃, suggesting significant nutrient loading, likely due to agricultural fertilizer runoff, fish processing waste, or sewage contamination.

4. Conclusion

This study presents a detailed assessment of spatio-temporal variability in water quality along the southeastern coast of Bangladesh. Across nine ecologically significant sites monitored over three consecutive dry-season months, 13 physicochemical parameters revealed marked spatial heterogeneity and temporal shifts. Salinity, conductivity, DO, and nutrient concentrations varied significantly, with post hoc analyses confirming that anthropogenic pressures drive distinct site-specific differences. Multivariate approaches, including PCA and cluster analysis, further distinguished ecological zones and identified major pollution sources, while the WPI classified several sites, particularly Naf Jetty and Shaplapur, as heavily polluted. These results emphasize the ecological vulnerability of intertidal mudflats and their resident mudskippers, which act as sensitive bioindicators of environmental health. In light of the observed pollution loads and their impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem function, the study recommends continuous site-specific monitoring, stricter regulation of aquaculture and land-based effluents, and integrated coastal zone management. Strengthened conservation measures and public awareness initiatives are essential to safeguarding these ecosystems, and the baseline data provided here will support future ecological assessments and inform evidence-based policy for sustaining Bangladesh’s coastal environments.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1: Physico-chemical parameters of the studied habitat of mudskipper (December 2023).

Parameters	Rezu Khal	Inani	Patuartek	Imamer dail	Monkhali	Shaplapur	Naf jetty/ Badir jetty	Shaporir dwip	Keary ghat
Temperature (°C)	25.9	25.8	25.9	25.9	27.2	25.8	25.8	25.7	25.9
Salinity (‰)	15	25	3	13	25	30	23	26	18
pH	8.09	7.68	8.41	8.08	7.31	7.92	8.4	7.78	8.08
DO (mg/L)	6.7	6.0	7.0	6.9	6.1	6.6	6.9	6.8	6.4
EC (mS)	22.80	38.0	4.56	19.76	38.0	45.60	34.96	39.52	27.36
Alkalinity (mg/L)	105	114	180	132	117	123	102	120	111
Chlorine (mg/L)	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3
Iron (mg/L)	0.37	1.43	0.41	3.08	0.53	0.54	0.29	0.90	1.69
PO ₄ -P (mg/L)	5.95	1.00	5.00	3.00	3.54	3.93	4.32	0.89	0.5
NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.04

NO ₂ -N(mg/L)	0.001	0.00	0.00	0.014	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SiO ₃ (mg/L)	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.47	0.07	0.03	0.05	0.15	0.17
NH ₃ (mg/L)	1	1	1	1.5	1	0.5	2	2.5	0.5

Table S2: Physico-chemical parameters of the studied habitat of mudskipper (January 2024).

Parameters	Rezu Khal	Inani	Patuartek	Imamer dail	Monkhali	Shaplapur	Naf jetty/ Badir jetty	Shaporir dwip	Keary ghat
Temperature (°C)	26.0	26.0	25.9	26.0	26.0	26.2	26.1	26.2	26.3
Salinity (‰)	34	1	1	6	14	18	28	33	23
pH	7.91	8.51	8.60	8.13	8.10	8.28	8.29	8.22	8.26
DO (mg/L)	6	6.7	6.9	6.2	7	6.8	6.5	6.8	6.7
EC (mS)	51.68	1.52	1.52	9.12	21.28	27.36	42.56	50.16	34.96
Alkalinity (mg/L)	138	90	00	00	84	00	00	00	120
Chlorine (mg/L)	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.5	0.5	2.0	0.5	0.3
Iron (mg/L)	3.5	0.29	2.6	0.2	3.0	2.5	3.5	0.76	0.55
PO ₄ -P (mg/L)	1	0.4	2	1	0.5	2.5	3.0	0.44	0.5
NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.06
NO ₂ -N(mg/L)	0.006	0.029	0.037	0.010	0.020	0.032	0.104	0.029	0.032
SiO ₃ (mg/L)	0.20	0.28	0.69	0.24	0.22	0.45	1.74	0.46	0.51
NH ₃ (mg/L)	0.00	0.21	0.37	0.43	0.89	1.10	2.37	2.24	1.77

Table S3: Physico-chemical parameters of the studied habitat of mudskipper (February 2024).

Parameters	Rezu Khal	Inani	Patuartek	Imamer dail	Monkhali	Shaplapur	Naf jetty/ Badir jetty	Shaporir dwip	Keary ghat
Temperature (°C)	25.9	25.8	25.8	25.9	26.0	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.2
Salinity (‰)	27	4	33	26	29	26	30	32	25
pH	8.13	8.41	7.81	7.92	7.55	7.83	7.88	7.85	7.90
DO (mg/L)	5.8	5.2	5.5	5.3	0.0	6.3	6.3	5.1	6.3
EC (mS)	41.04	6.08	50.16	39.52	44.08	39.52	45.60	48.64	38.0
Alkalinity (mg/L)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Chlorine (mg/L)	0.2	0.2	0.4	1.0	0.0	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.3
Iron (mg/L)	0.16	0.62	0.29	0.65	0.54	0.72	1.28	0.85	0.72
PO ₄ -P (mg/L)	1.81	3.67	1.51	4.45	0.00	2.71	1.00	0.5	0.5
NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.05	0.46	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.04

NO ₂ -N(mg/L)	2.020	0.024	0.028	0.48	0.037	0.031	0.043	0.041	0.029
SiO ₃ (mg/L)	0.00	0.12	0.07	0.17	1.88	0.04	1.11	0.28	0.35
NH ₃ (mg/L)	1.67	0.44	1.0	2.69	2.71	1.63	0.04	0.5	2.05

Table S4: Component matrix of four factors model with strong to moderate loadings in the mudskipper habitat of the Bay of Bengal.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.748	28.831	28.831
2	2.038	15.676	44.507
3	1.798	13.829	58.337
4	1.459	11.224	69.561
5	1.076	8.275	77.837

References

- Abdullah, A. H., Chowdhury, G., Adikari, D., Jahan, I., Andrawina, Y. O., Hossain, M. A., Schneider, P., & Iqbal, M. M. (2022). Macroplastics Pollution in the Surma River in Bangladesh: A Threat to Fish Diversity and Freshwater Ecosystems. *Water (Switzerland)*, 14(20), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14203263>
- Adesakin, T. A., Oyewale, A. T., Bayero, U., Mohammed, A. N., Aduwo, I. A., Ahmed, P. Z., ... & Barje, I. B. (2020). Assessment of bacteriological quality and phycochemical parameters of domestic water sources in Samaru community, Zaria, Northwest Nigeria. *Heliyon*, 6(8).
- Akhter, S., Qiao, F., Wu, K., Yin, X., Chowdhury, K. M. A., & Chowdhury, N. U. M. K. (2021). Seasonal and long-term sea-level variations and their forcing factors in the northern Bay of Bengal: A statistical analysis of temperature, salinity, wind stress curl, and regional climate index data. *Dynamics of Atmospheres and Oceans*, 95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DYNATMOCE.2021.101239>
- Alongi, D. M. (2012). Carbon sequestration in mangrove forests. *Carbon Management*, 3(3), 313–322. <https://doi.org/10.4155/CMT.12.20;WGROU:STRING:PUBLICATION>
- Ansari, A. A., Trivedi, S., Saggi, S., & Rehman, H. (2014). Mudskipper: A biological indicator for environmental monitoring and assessment of coastal waters. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies (Vol. 2, Issue 6)*. www.entomoljournal.com
- Bhuyan, M.S., Islam, M.T., Mahadevan, G., Siddiqui, A.A.M., Peas, M.H., Mojumder, I.A. (2024). Morphometric identification of mudskippers recorded from the Cox's Bazar coast, Bay of Bengal, Bangladesh: Challenges and recommendations. *Natural Resources Conservation and Research*, 7(2), 10014. <https://doi.org/10.24294/nrcr10014>
- BIS, I. S. (2003). Specification for drinking water (IS: 10500). New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standard (BIS), 1-5.

- Boyacioglu, H. (2007). Development of a water quality index based on a European classification scheme. *Water SA*, 33(1), 101–106. <https://doi.org/10.4314/SA.V33I1.47882>
- Chaudhuri, A., Mukherjee, S., Marina, & Homechaudhuri, S. (2013). Seasonal dynamics of fish assemblages in an intertidal mudflat of Indian Sundarbans. *Scientia Marina*, 77(2), 301–311. <https://doi.org/10.3989/scimar.03766.15A>
- Dabruzzi, T. F., Wygoda, M. L., Wright, J. E., Eme, J., & Bennett, W. A. (2011). Direct evidence of cutaneous resistance to evaporative water loss in amphibious mud skipper (family Gobiidae) and rockskipper (family Blenniidae) fishes from Pulau Hoga, southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 406(1–2), 125–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEMBE.2011.05.032>
- Dewiyanti, I., Melanie, K., Almuniro, S., Damora, A., Nufadillah, N., & Batubra, A. S. (2022). Growth patterns and condition factor of the mudskipper (*Periophthalmus gracilis*) in mangrove ecosystem rehabilitation areas in Banda Aceh and Aceh Besar, Indonesia. *Fisheries & Aquatic Life*, 30(2), 85–94. <https://doi.org/10.2478/AOPF-2022-0008>
- Elviana, S., Sunarni, S., Maturbongs, M. R., Sajriawati, & Fakhriyyah, S. (2019). Mudskipper diversity and its relationship to an environmental condition in estuary. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 343(1), 012191. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/343/1/012191>
- Gouletquer, P., & Le Moine, O. (2002). Shellfish farming and Coastal Zone Management (CZM) development in the Marennes-Oléron Bay and Charentais Sounds (Charente Maritime, France): A review of recent developments. *Aquaculture International*, 10(6), 507–525. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1023975418669/METRICS>
- Graham, J. (1997). *Air-breathing fishes: evolution, diversity, and adaptation*. Academic Press, San Diego.
- Hamidah, A., Murni, P., & Said, M. (2024). The Diversity of Mudskipper Fish Family Gobiidae in Mangrove Area, Seberang District, Tanjung Jabung Regency, West Jambi. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.53555/SFS.V11I01.2045>
- He, L., Mukai, T., Hou Chu, K., Ma, Q., & Zhang, J. (2015). Biogeographical role of the Kuroshio Current in the amphibious mudskipper *Periophthalmus modestus* indicated by mitochondrial DNA data. *Scientific Reports*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.10138/srep15645>
- He, Q., & Silliman, B. R. (2019). Climate Change, Human Impacts, and Coastal Ecosystems in the Anthropocene. *Current Biology*, 29(19), R1021–R1035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CUB.2019.08.042>
- Hossain, M., & Patra, P. K. (2020). Water pollution index-A new integrated approach to

- rank water quality. *Ecological Indicators*, 117, 106668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOLIND.2020.106668>
- Karim, M. A., Uddin, M. H., Barua, S., Nath, B., Chowdhury, A. I., Hoque, M. A., & Mofizur Rahman, I. S. M. A. I. L. (2019). Pollution and Source Identification of Halda River Water of Bangladesh Using Field Observation, Laboratory Analysis and GIS Technique. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, 35(5).
- Le Pape, O., Holley, J., Guérault, D., & Désaunay, Y. (2003). Quality of coastal and estuarine essential fish habitats: estimations based on the size of juvenile common sole (*Solea solea* L.). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 58(4), 793–803. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7714\(03\)00185-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7714(03)00185-9)
- Levy, D. A., & Northcote, T. G. (1982). Juvenile salmon residency in a marsh area of the Fraser River estuary. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 39(2), 270-276. <https://doi.org/10.1139/F82-038>
- McLusky, D. S. (1989). The Estuarine Environment. *The Estuarine Ecosystem*, 1-48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-7616-3-1>
- Moore, J., Bird, D. L., Dobbis, S. K., & Woodward, G. (2017). Nonpoint source contributions drive elevated major ion and dissolved inorganic carbon concentrations in urban watersheds. *Environmental Science & Technology Letters*, 4(6), 198-204. DOI: 10.1021/acs.estlett.7b00096
- Murdy, E. O. (1989). A taxonomic revision and cladistic analysis of the oxudercine gobies (Gobiidae: Oxudercinae).
- Nay, T. J., Gervais, C. R., Hoey, A. S., Johansen, J. L., Steffensen, J. F., & Rummer, J. L. (2018). The emergence emergency: A mudskipper's response to temperatures. *Journal of Thermal Biology*, 78, 65–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JTHERBIO.2018.09.005>
- Oghenetekevwe, E., Davies Ibienebo, C., & Orororo Clement, O. (2024). Water quality assessment and heavy metal levels in mudskipper (*Periophthalmus papilio*), sediments and water of mangrove swamps, Rivers state, Nigeria. <https://doi.org/10.52589/AJENSR-CZHQP9M>
- Pattaratumrong, M. S., & Pompha, T. (2024). Habitat of the amphibious mudskipper *Periophthalmus schlosseri* in Songkhla Lake, Thailand. *Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity*, 25(5), 1875–1881. <https://doi.org/10.13057/BIODIV/D250503>
- Paul, B. G., & Vogl, C. R. (2011). Impacts of shrimp farming in Bangladesh: Challenges and alternatives. *Ocean and Coastal Management*, 54(3), 201–211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.OCECOAMAN.2010.12.001>
- Pesce, S. F., & Wunderlin, D. A. (2000). Use of water quality indices to verify the impact of Córdoba City (Argentina) on Suquia River. *Water Research*, 34(11),

2915–2926.[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(00\)00036-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(00)00036-1)

- Polgar, G., Sacchetti, A., & Galli, P. (2010). Differentiation and adaptive radiation of amphibious gobies (Gobiidae: Oxudercinae) in semi-terrestrial habitats. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 77(7), 1645-1664.
- Rabalais, N. N., Díaz, R. J., Levin, L. A., Turner, R. E., Gilbert, D., & Zhang, J. (2010). Dynamics and distribution of natural and human-caused hypoxia. *Biogeosciences*, 7(2), 585–619. <https://doi.org/10.5194/BG-7-585-2010>
- Rodionova, O., Kucheryavskiy, S., & Pomerantsev, A. (2021). Efficient tools for principal component analysis of complex data-A tutorial. *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, 213, 104304.
- Saha, N., & Rahman, M. S. (2018). Multivariate statistical analysis of metal contamination in surface water around Dhaka export processing industrial zone, Bangladesh. *Environmental nanotechnology, monitoring & management*, 10, 206-211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enmm.2018.07.007>
- Saifullah, M. K., Tasnim, N., Tasnim, A., Pandit, D., Sultana, M. A., Hossain, M. A., ... & Kunda, M. (2025). Seasonal variation, and ecological risks assessment of heavy metals pollution in an upstream tropical freshwater river, Bangladesh. *International Journal of River Basin Management*, 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15715124.2025.2523413>
- Santoso, H. B., Krisdianto, K., & Yunita, R. (2024). Iron bioaccumulation and ecological implications in the coastal swamp wetlands ecosystem of South Kalimantan: Insights from giant mudskipper fish as bioindicators. *Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management*, 11(3), 5539-5550. <https://doi.org/10.15243/jdmlm.2024.113.5539>
- Santoso, H.B, Suhartono, E., Yunita, R., & Biyatmoko, D. (2020). Mudskipper fish as a bio-indicator for heavy metals pollution in a coastal wetland. *Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Biology and Fisheries*, 24(7-Special issue), 1073-1095. 10.21608/ejabf.2020.144402
- Siddique, M. A. M., Ahmed, M., Biswas, S., & Hossain, M. S. (2024). Heavy metals in three estuarine mudskipper species from Hatiya Island, Bay of Bengal: Public health at risk. *Regional Studies in Marine Science*, 71, 103411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RMA.2024.103411>
- Simeonov, V., Stratis, J. A., Samara, C., Zachariadis, G., Voutsas, D., Anthemidis, A., Sofoniou, M., & Kouimtzis, T. (2003). Assessment of the surface water quality in Northern Greece. *Water Research*, 37(17), 4119–4124. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(03\)00398-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(03)00398-1)
- Souza, T. (2025). Principal Component Analysis (PCA). In *Advanced Statistical Analysis for Soil Scientists* (pp. 43-56). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Tran, L. T., & Dinh, Q. M. (2021). Population structure of *Periophthalmodon schlosseri*

(Perciformes: Gobiidae) in Soc Trang province, Vietnam. <https://doi.org/10.5555/20210530820>

Uddin, M. N., Alam, M. S., Mobin, M. N., & Miah, M. A. (2014). An Assessment of the River Water Quality Parameters: A case of Jamuna River. *Journal of Environmental Science and Natural Resources*, 7(1), 249–256. <https://doi.org/10.3329/JESNR.V7I1.22179>

Yamashita et al., (2018). Coarser grains better resist wave energy and tend to accumulate. *Science and Natural Resources*, 7(1), 249–256. <https://doi.org/10.3329/JESNR.V7I1.22179>

World Health Organization. (2011). WHO guidelines on preventing early pregnancy and poor reproductive health outcomes among adolescents in developing countries. World Health Organization.

WHO, (2011). Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality, fourth ed. World Health Organization, Geneva.